

Analytical strategy for sample preparation in trace metal analysis[†]

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Abstract : A two phase extraction of Ni^{II} from aqueous to non ionic surfactant is carried out as a sample preparation step prior to determination of Ni^{II} in different matrices. The Ni^{II}-Schiff base complex formed in the aqueous phase was subsequently transferred to the Triton X-100 phase. The process was optimized for operational variables viz. pH, concentration of the surfactant as well as the ligand, incubation time and temperature. The cloud point temperature was evaluated in presence of different electrolytes with varying concentrations. Both the salting-in and salting-out agents were tested to optimize the cloud point temperature and maximize the extraction efficiency. Extraction efficiency was more than 95%. The negative free energy change indicates that the process is favorable and spontaneous one. The process is applied for extraction and preconcentration of Ni^{II} from alloy, water and soil sample.

Keywords : Micellar extraction, Ni^{II}-Schiff base complex, Triton X-100, optimization, thermodynamic feasibility.

Introduction

Anthropogenic contribution of heavy metals into the environment far exceeding the natural inputs is a real threat of the present century¹. Route sources of heavy metals in the environment include river input, local runoff, atmospheric deposition² and industrial effluents³. The role of any metal ion, whether essential or toxic, depends on its level and the form in a particular matrix. Metallic nickel is reasonably anticipated to be a human carcinogen and there is an increased incidence of malignant and benign tumors or a combination of the both at multiple tissue sites in multiple species of experimental animals if administered by intratracheal instillation, subcutaneous, intramuscular, or intraperitoneal injection. Anderson *et al.*⁴ reported that nickel refinery workers exposed primarily to soluble nickel compounds had a significant excess risk of lung and nasal cancer⁵. The importance of metal ion determination in environmental compartments as well as in biological samples is increasing not only to understand its load but also to predict the appropriate behavior of the matrix. This usually requires a sample preparation step via preconcentration prior to its determination even through sensitive instrumental techniques. The technologies employed generally are precipitation⁶, solvent ex-

traction⁷, solid phase extraction⁸, ion-exchange separation⁹, electrochemical method¹⁰, high-performance liquid chromatography¹¹, ion chromatography¹². These being neither economical nor ecofriendly¹³, always requires an alternative technique that is simple, efficient and low cost. The merit of the process increases manifold if it follows a green route as in case of cloud point extraction (CPE).

Extraction of solute using two phase aqueous micellar system at some specified temperature, known as cloud point extraction (CPE), is proved to be an important operation in the field of separation following enrichment/preconcentration together with recovery of the analyte. The process is simple and environment friendly. The performance of the operation can be optimized and controlled varying solution conditions. CPE of metals for preconcentration/separation generally is achieved via formation of the hydrophobic complexes using suitable chelating ligands¹⁴.

The self assembling aggregates of surfactant molecule i.e. the micelle, being capable of selective interactions with different molecules strongly modify solubility, chemical equilibrium and may change kinetics and spectroscopic behavior of the solutes. The hydrophilic tail flocks inside

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

(to minimize the unfavorable contact with water) while the hydrophobic head stays in the outer core (in order to maximize contact with the aqueous medium) of the micelle¹⁵. Micelle formation reflects a delicate balance of several intermolecular forces such as van der Waals, electrostatic, steric and/or hydrophobic forces¹⁶. Aqueous solution of almost all non ionic and some zwitterionic surfactants become turbid when heated to a specific temperature known as the cloud point temperature (CPT). Above this temperature the isotropic micellar solution separates into two transparent liquid phases; a surfactant rich phase of very small volume (composed mostly of the surfactant plus a small amount of water) in equilibrium with an aqueous phase, which contains surfactant concentration close to critical micelle concentration¹⁷.

Preconcentration is achieved in CPE as the solute is transferred and accumulated in a small volume of the surfactant rich phase. Preconcentration, in general, may be considered as an effective sample preparation tool as it improves the sensitivity of analyte determination and enhances the lower limit of detection¹⁸. The additional advantages of CPE are that it does not require any organic solvent and eliminates generation of sludge. These features make the operation a clean and green one. The present communication deals with CPE efficiency of Ni^{II} via complexation with a Schiff base ligand viz. *N,N'*-bis(salicylaldehyde)ethylenediamine (Salen). The optimum condition (pH, concentration of surfactant, ligand and metal) at the equilibrium time and CPT was set up. The process was applied for spiked as well as real sample and the preconcentration factor is evaluated.

Results and discussion

Influence of operational variables :

The CPE of metal ion essentially requires formation of a complex for distribution between aqueous and surfactant rich phase under equilibrium condition. The CPE efficiency depends on the hydrophobicity of the metal complex, kinetics of complex formation, apparent equilibrium constant in the micellar medium and rate of transfer of the complex from aqueous to the surfactant rich phase, following a pathway almost similar to that of conventional liquid-liquid extraction¹⁹. Optimization of operational variables viz. pH, surfactant concentration, concentration of ligand, incubation time and temperature for

the formation and distribution of complex is needed to achieve maximum efficiency of the process. Schiff bases represent a versatile class of chelating ligand for the main group and transition metals²⁰. Here Salen, a Schiff base ligand, is primarily chosen due to its ease of preparation, quantitative yield, stoichiometric composition, hydrophobic nature and stability of Ni^{II}-Schiff base complex. All these features are expected to suitably facilitate the transfer of the Ni^{II} complex from aqueous to the hydrophobic core of the micellar aggregate. pH plays a unique role in metal-chelate formation and hence extraction yield as well as preconcentration is influenced by the solution pH²¹. The effect of pH on the extraction behavior was investigated in the pH range 2–10 (Fig. 1). The extraction increases with an increase of the solution pH until an optimum value was reached at about 8.0. The concentration of ligand (C_{ligand}) is varied upto 40.0 mM in the present study. It is found that as the concentration increases the extraction percent increases and reaches a maxima corresponding to a value of 10.0 mM with an extraction yield of 95% (Fig. 2). However, the ligand concentration higher to the stoichiometric ratio is chosen in subsequent experiments to facilitate complexation and maintain the stability of the complex in the aqueous-surfactant assembly. The extraction efficiency was examined varying Triton X-100 concentration ($C_{\text{surfactant}}$) in the range of 0.5–5% (v/v). Quantitative extraction corresponds to 4.0% of Triton X-100 is observed (Fig. 3). At lower surfactant concentration the extraction was low, probably due to inadequate micellar assemblies to quantitatively entrap the complex. However, at higher Triton X-100 concentration the extraction efficiency decreases due to dilution effect.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH.

Fig. 2. Effect of ligand concentration.

Fig. 4. Effect of incubation time.

Fig. 3. Effect of Triton X-100 concentration.

Fig. 5. Effect of incubation temperature.

Incubation of solution at a certain temperature for a certain period of time facilitates cloud formation and adequate phase separation in CPE. The range of temperature and time were selected from 323 to 363 K and 5 to 45 min respectively. It is found that at the optimized pH, concentration of metal, ligand and Triton X-100 a heating period of 30 min (Fig. 4) at 348 ± 20 K (Fig. 5) and cooling for 20 min in an ice-bath leads to maximum recovery.

Presence of salts and ionic strength of the solution may influence CPE via modification of cloud point temperature²². The role of different electrolytes on the extent of Ni^{II} extraction was evaluated using some common electrolytes viz. NaCl, KCl, KNO_3 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ in Table 1. In all the cases a fixed concentration of electrolyte (1.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}) was added to the solution prior to CPE. It is found that cloud point temperature and the extraction yield depend on the nature of the added

Table 1. Influence of electrolyte on CPT and extraction of metal complex

Salt added	CPT (K)	Extraction (%)
–	344 ± 2	81.2
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	336 ± 2	95.2
KCl	337 ± 3	71.6
NaCl	338 ± 1	69.3
KNO_3	358 ± 2	81.6

electrolyte. Presence of chloride, sulfate, carbonate typically depress the cloud point, due to their salting-out effect, in proportion to their concentration. The lower the lyotropic number of the electrolyte, the greater is the effect. On the other hand, salting-in type electrolytes, such as nitrate, iodide and thiocyanate, typically increase the cloud point temperature²³. As addition of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ provides lower cloud point temperature and highest extraction it is used as an effective salting-out agent in all subsequent experiments. The role of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concen-

Fig. 6. Effect of salt concentration.

tration (C_{salt}) on the extraction percent is presented in Fig. 6. Smaller amount of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ results insufficient extraction probably due to limited clouding. Larger amount of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ beyond the optimum concentration, however, shows no change in percent extraction.

The presence of surfactant does not influence spectral determination of metal complex. But as the surfactant rich phase is very viscous, a definite portion of methanol is added to the solution and transferred to the spectrophotometric cell for operation in the visible region. Similarly for AAS operation methanol containing nitric acid ($1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was added to the surfactant rich phase after CPE in order to facilitate aspiration and introduction of the solution to the nebulizer.

Effect of foreign ions :

CPE efficiency of metal may be influenced by the presence of different foreign ions. The limit of tolerance in respect to initial metal concentration ($50 \mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$) in the present case for different ions is evaluated as : Na^+ and K^+ : $1000 \mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$; Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} and Cr^{3+} : $500 \mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$; Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Pb^{2+} : $20 \mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$; PO_4^{3-} , CH_3COO^- and $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$: $100 \mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$.

Analytical figure or merit :

The efficiency of the process was found from the spiked samples of different concentrations. At the 95% confidence level and for five degree of freedom the recovery of Ni^{II} was found to be between 94–95% with a standard deviation less than 0.05 (Table 2).

Effectiveness of the process is defined by the limit of

Table 2. Determination of metal in spiked samples

Sl. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$)			Recovery (%)
	Mean	Spiked	Found	
1.	50.0	0.0	47.50 ± 0.023	95.0
2.	50.0	1.0	47.40 ± 0.046	94.8
3.	50.0	3.0	47.40 ± 0.036	94.8
4.	50.0	5.0	47.30 ± 0.028	94.6
5.	50.0	10.0	47.20 ± 0.044	94.4

detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ). LOD and LOQ of the developed procedure were calculated taking eight consecutive measurements of the blank signal, the background equivalent concentration (B) and relative standard deviation (R) according to the expressions presented below :

$$B = (\text{average blank intensity})/(\text{slope of the analytical curve})$$

$$\text{LOD} = (3.B.R)/100$$

$$\text{LOQ} = (10.B.R)/100$$

The preconcentration factors (P.F.), defined as the ratio of the slope of the analytical curve before and after preconcentration was evaluated in each case. The characteristic features of the proposed method is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Analytical features of the proposed method

Feature	Ni^{II}
Regression equation	$0.008 C_0 \pm 0.017$
Linear range ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$)	3.3–115.0
Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$)	0.15
Relative standard deviation (%)	0.04
Preconcentration factor	48
$C_0 = 50 \mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$	

Applicability of the proposed method :

The applicability of the proposed method is judged from some real sample of Ni^{II} . Some typical waste water, sediment and alloy samples are analyzed for the recovery and preconcentration. The sample composition and the source are indicated in the Table 4.

Feasibility of the operation :

Distribution ratio (D) value for the extraction of Ni^{II} -Salen complex is found to be 9.73. The negative free energy change ($-\Delta G$) value of 6.88 kJ mol^{-1} indicates the extraction operation is favorable and spontaneous.

Table 4. Recovery and preconcentration of nickel(II) from industrial waste, alloy and soil sample

Sample	Composition	Recovery (%)	Std. dev. (n=6)	P.F.
Industrial effluent (Electroplating waste)	CN ⁻ : 0.2; NH ₄ ⁺ -N : 50; Cd ²⁺ : 18.01; Pb ²⁺ : 11.2; Zn ²⁺ : 4.0; Cu ²⁺ : 10.0; Cd ²⁺ : 14.0; Ni ²⁺ : 62.2; pH : 7.89; S.S : 100 (in mg dm ⁻³ except pH)	93.3	0.039	47
Sediment (Industrial area)	Org C : 3.32; N : 21.2; Cd ²⁺ : 12.01; Pb ²⁺ : 8.4; Zn ²⁺ : 5.6; Cu ²⁺ : 14.3; Cd ²⁺ : 10.1; Ni ²⁺ : 37.9; pH : 7.86 (in mg dm ⁻³ except pH)	94.2	0.041	45
Alloy (NBS SRM-94C)	Mn : 0.014; Sn : 0.006; Al : 4.13; Cd : 0.002; Fe : 0.018; Pb : 0.006; Mg : 0.042; Ni : 0.006 (in %)	95.1	0.038	48

Experimental

Apparatus :

The spectral measurements were performed in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model Shimadzu, UV-2401PC). Ni^{II} concentration in the experimental solution was determined with a flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Varian AA1407) using an air-acetylene flame and hollow cathode lamp as the radiation source at a wave length of 232.0 nm. The pH measurements were made with a Systronics pH meter (Model 335).

Reagents :

The reagents are of analytical grade and obtained from E. Merck, India. Stock standard solution was prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of NiSO₄·7H₂O in deionised water. Working solutions were prepared by proper dilution of the stock. The non-ionic surfactant, Triton X-100 was used without further purification. Salen, the Schiff base ligand, was synthesized as per the literature²⁴.

Synthesis of the ligand :

The Schiff base ligand (Salen) was synthesized via condensation of ethylene diamine with salicylaldehyde in 1 : 3 molar ratio under reflux condition in methanol for 3 h. The solids appeared on cooling were subsequently filtered, washed and dried in a desiccator over fused CaCl₂. The ligand thus prepared was recrystallized and characterized by elemental analysis, melting point determination, infra-red and visible absorption spectral data.

Procedure for Ni^{II} extraction :

An aliquot of 15 cm³ solution containing a definite

proportion of metal and the ligand, buffered with desired pH was mixed with Triton X-100 of suitable concentrations. The solution was taken in a typical glass tube, shaken for 5 min and left to stand in a thermostatic bath at 348 ± 2 K for 30 min. As the cloud formation occurs the solution was cooled immediately in an ice-bath. The surfactant-rich phase became viscous and was retained at the bottom of the tube. The aqueous and the surfactant rich phase are completely separated. Ni^{II} content in the surfactant rich phase was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Conclusion

Use of CPE procedure offers a unique technique for separation and recovery of Ni^{II} from aqueous solution which includes low cost, safety, preconcentration with high recoveries and very good extraction efficiency. The process was optimized for operational variables. The characteristic features including detection limit and tolerance level are evaluated. The proposed method is applied for preconcentration prior to the determination of Ni^{II} in spiked and real samples. The process avoids use of toxic organic solvent as in conventional liquid-liquid extraction and is therefore a clean technique.

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